

A review of the Impacts of COVID-19: Lessons for Africa

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic currently ravaging the world and its economy has claimed the lives of over 360,000 with over 5 million reported cases globally. It reportedly originated from man’s encroachment into biodiversity habitat like other similar pandemics such as Ebola, SARS. The pandemic has led to the imposition of total lockdown over many cities across the world. The imposition has led to improved air quality such as the decline in N₂O, CO₂ and noise pollution across the world. The Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has vindicated the air pollution scientists and conservation advocates that anthropogenic activities drive changes in the global environment with the attendant health risks. It has also revealed the vulnerabilities of the world population to health care, economy and food supply. Again, the virus has affected Africa so much and has revealed that intervention is required in many socio-economic spheres. It exposed the need for social security, food security, potable water and improved hygiene and the need for higher investment in agriculture and education. The paper calls for more commitment from African and of course world leaders to bridge the gap between the ‘haves’ and the ‘have-nots’ and approve funds for environmental change and conservation researchers and scholars in pursuit of proactive measures for such emergencies in the future.

Keywords: COVID-19, pandemic, land use, environmental change, air pollution.

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1. Introduction

The novel COVID-19 popularly referred to as Coronavirus disease is a virus that invades the humans by attacking the respiratory system; leading to difficulty in breathing and often death. It all started in faraway Wuhan in China in December 2019 from where it spread to other parts of the world. Currently, it has claimed the lives of over 360,000 with nearly 6 million reported cases globally (Henriques, 2020; WHO, 2020a, 2020b)[1-3]. Africa is not left out with the death of over 1500 (AU, 2020) [4] though the casualty level is not as high as it is elsewhere. However, there is cause to worry as the number of infected persons is rising exponentially such that on March 27th, the record was 500000 cases with over 24000 deaths (Corlett et al., 2020; Lucchese and Pianta, 2020) [5, 6], but, barely a month later, it has jumped to over 197000 deaths and 2.8 million cases as at 24th April 2020 and to nearly 6 million cases and 367000 deaths by May 31st (WHO, 2020a, 2020b) [2, 3].

Many nations have imposed total lockdown to curtail its spread, Africa not left out. However, such a measure is taking a great toll on the economy with a prospect of an austere future (Lucchese and Pianta, 2020) [6]. The pandemic is anticipated to be followed by a severe unprecedented economic crisis (Lucchese and Pianta, 2020) [6]. and impending famine in many developing countries. Notwithstanding excellent evaluation of the likely economic crisis and the spread that will accompany the pandemic (Bai et al., 2020; Lucchese and Pianta, 2020; WHO, 2020b) [7, 6, 3]., little has been done in the area of the pandemic's impact on land-use (agriculture, forest and Savanna ecosystem, water), education and food security in Africa. The crisis will significantly impact meeting the targets of the SDGs Agenda 2030 of zero hunger (Sumner et al., 2020) [8], clean water and sanitation, climate actions and partnerships for the goals among others.

The pandemic has exposed the weakness of the global health and welfare systems and non-existence of global rules and coordination on the protection of health, from the animals' markets in China and the swiftness to address an epidemic (Lucchese and Pianta, 2020) [6]. They further argued that to address the impending crises requires rewriting the rules of globalization (Cooper, 2020) [9] such that health, welfare, labor rights and the environments be protected by

international standards. However, the promulgation of rules or conventions may be of little good without the will power to bridge the gap between the 'haves' and the 'have-nots'. The first thing should be the total end to the exploitation of the poor people and the poor nations.

Nevertheless, the poor nations too should brace-up for the challenges ahead after the pandemic. The fact remains that the world is changing and the conservation community (Corlett et al., 2020) [5] and climate/environmental scientists must be ready to respond accordingly. Likewise, for the academics/researchers, education administrators and world leaders and of course every individual in terms of attitudinal change to land-use/environmental change issues and care for the environment.

2. Evidence of, or probable impacts on the environment

Though difficult to completely ascertain at this stage, there are reports that the global pollution levels have reduced due to limited activities resulting from the lockdown. A clear example has been the pollution level in Italy, USA and China which has reduced (Corlett et al., 2020; Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) [5, 10]. Although there has been limited research, like no fieldwork or limited laboratory experiments, there have been reports of reduced human pressures on natural ecosystems, cleaner air and water, and wildlife reclaiming denied habitats (Corlett et al., 2020) [5]. Another immediate impact is the cancellation of climate change and environmental scientists' meetings and conferences. While online conferencing are in use, the limitations cannot be overemphasized compared to the interactions and networking associated with in-person conferences (Corlett et al., 2020) [5] which is valuable to early career researchers.

The pandemic has led to the cancellation of major intergovernmental and UN climate conferences; for instance, the COP15 and COP26 earlier scheduled this October/November in China and Glasgow respectively. These cancellations have consequences on the planned efforts to address climate change challenges (Corlett et al., 2020) [5]. Also, waste management and recycling have been suspended in many cities in Europe and the

USA (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) [10]. There is an increased generation of domestic and hospital wastes due to quarantine measures and increased use of protective equipment (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) [10]. Wastewater treatment is also affected in some cities like increased use of chlorine for treatment in China (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) [10] with the attendant health implications.

However, on the positive side, there have been reports of improved air quality due to pollution reduction in many cities as revealed by satellite images (Figure 1) (Corlett et al., 2020; NASA, 2020) [5, 11]. A reduction in the CO₂ level has been reported across many cities (Mitra et al., 2020) [12]. Though this decline in pollution level will be short-lived (Analytica, 2020) [13], it is a pointer to the extent which anthropogenic

activities have led to a deterioration of the natural environment and drive emissions of gases and aerosols into the atmosphere. The pandemic's terrible effect notwithstanding, it justified environmental change and conservation advocates that man's activity is endangering life on earth. Thus, more funding is required for environmental change scientists for research and conservation and the protection of environmental resources. There has been an observable reduction in pressure to beaches which have hitherto been overexploited and reduction in noise pollution in many locations (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) [10]. For instance, the buzzing noise of Lagos city and the noise from vehicles, airplanes and firms all disappeared with the imposition of lockdown.

Figure 1. N₂O concentration across eastern China before the quarantine and during the quarantine.

Source: Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument on ESA's Sentinel-5 satellite, NASA Earth Observatory images by Joshua Stevens. [11]

3. The Covid-19 pandemic and food security

The pandemic has exposed a lot of inadequacies and susceptibilities of the world population to health care, economy and food supply (Miles, 2020) [14]. The committee on world food security reported that the supply and demand for food would be severely affected in an unclear way in the future (Miles, 2020) [14]. Yet, it's been asserted that agricultural expansion and human occupation into the wild ecosystems, together with the way we produce food, is leading to the emergence of deadly pathogens and the eventual spread (Miles, 2020; Rohr et al., 2019) [14, 15]. Some of these infections include Ebola, multiple swine flu variants (H1N1, H1N2), Asian Avian Influenza, Nipah virus among others (Miles, 2020; Rohr et al., 2019) [14, 15]. Agriculture

contributes nearly 30% of the GHGs emissions which compromise the air, water and soil quality, ecosystem function, biodiversity loss, erosion, desertification and developmental disorders in children (Tilman et al., 2001; Zhang et al., 2007; Peeters, 2018; Blüher, 2019; Fears et al., 2019; Corlett et al., 2020; Miles, 2020) [16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 5, 14]. It is also likely that some countries may face famine after the pandemic due to quarantine, which has limited production, farming activities, sale or limited access to farm inputs.

4. The Covid-19 Pandemic: Lessons for Africa and the way forward

Agricultural expansion and population explosion remain the major driving forces for land-use

change and environmental change (Tilman et al., 2001; Foley et al., 2011; Rohr et al., 2019; Fears et al., 2019; Miles, 2020) [16, 21, 15, 20, 14]. The encroachment of agriculture and human settlement to biodiversity habitat is a menace that has been linked to several epidemics in recent times including the current Covid-19, linked to wild animals' markets in Wuhan, China (Corlett et al., 2020) [5]. Agriculture currently occupies half the global land and uses more than two-thirds of its freshwater (Alexandratos and Bruinsma, 2012) [22]. The problem is intertwined, for notwithstanding the agricultural expansion, more than a billion people in the world are malnourished, which a greater percentage is in Africa (Myers et al., 2015; WHO, 2018; Rohr et al., 2019) [23, 24, 15]. The UN project the world population to reach over 11 billion by 2100 with Africa reaching 4.4 billion (Millington and Cleland, 2017; UN, 2017) [25, 26]. To meet the SDG goal of poverty eradication in Africa demands a change of attitude and approach. It requires increased investment in agriculture to promote agricultural intensification rather than expansion (Foley et al., 2011; WHO, 2018) [21, 24]. Thus, governments across Africa should work together with a commitment to promote conservation and agricultural intensification by increasing agricultural budget/investment. The challenges of feeding the 4.4 billion persons and managing infectious diseases are complex. Currently, intensification and expansion of agriculture occur disproportionately in the tropical developing world (Tilman et al., 2001; Gibbs et al., 2010; Rohr et al., 2019) [16, 25, 15] with 75% of death attributed to infectious disease (Lozano et al., 2012; Knutie et al., 2017) [27, 28]. However, Africa has the potential to stabilize ecosystems by limiting agricultural expansion into her rich Savanna and rainforest areas. This can be achieved by agricultural intensification (Foley et al., 2011) [21] with the use of improved inputs. Africa's rich ecosystem if saved from massive destruction could be vital to the ecosystem and environmental quality restoration and avert health issues like the Ebola experience a few years ago. Prospects lie in nature-based solutions (Cooper, 2020) [9].

5. Conclusion

Despite the evidence of environmental change, not much has been done to reduce the impact notwithstanding pre-warnings in the past of its

health implications (Haines, 1991; Scheelbeek, 2020) [30, 31]. For instance, the pledged Nationally Determined Contributions to reducing GHG emissions, part of the 2015 Paris Agreement on climate change is yet to be fully implemented. Some nations are threatening to pull out of the agreement while several others show less commitment. Yet the global temperature is likely to rise to over 3⁰C above the pre-industrial level by the end of the century (Olhoff and Christensen, 2018; Christensen and Olhoff, 2019) [32, 33]. The potential impacts of the Covid-19 both direct and indirect are difficult to ascertain as has been argued in the literature that associated mental risks may be high (Bao et al., 2020; Rajkumar, 2020) [34, 35]. Additionally, it may spring attitudinal change and thoughts about man's relationships with the environment that may scale up the implementation and the actualization of the SDGs. It has shown that globalization has its limitations and thus, African leaders must have to invest more in water and hygiene (Cooper, 2020) [9], environment/air quality, internet, and education/research. As Universities elsewhere were having lectures and seminars online, several Universities in Africa are shut down or struggling with a poor internet connection. There might also be an increase in insecurity, thefts and overexploitation of the natural resources if no checks are put in place as millions have lost their jobs. This brings to the fore the need for African leaders to make provisions for social security and create more jobs after the pandemic by diversifying their economy. Thus, to avoid the impending famine that might occur in a post-COVID Africa, our leaders and academics must re-strategies on how best to improve food production in the continent without necessarily harming the ecosystem. This will help the continent achieve food-sufficiency and avoid an outbreak of similar pandemic associated with encroachments to nature and biodiversity. In this regard, more funding should also be made available to environmental change researchers and scholars. Thus, increased investment in agriculture, education and scientific research is key to revamp the economy in the post-COVID Africa. Personal hygiene and sanitation should be promoted everywhere and the commitment to bridge the gap between the poor and the rich is critical. Finally, strong internet and widespread access should be a priority to avoid preventable losses in any case of similar experience in the future where Universities would be completely

closed and communication hampered due to poor connections. Thus, a resilient society should be the target of the leaders towards achieving the SDGs most especially as immigration and international relations among nations may plummet in post-COVID-19 world.

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